

SJIF Impact Factor(2023) : 8.224

ISI I.F.Value : 1.188

ISSN (Online): 2455-3662

DOI : 10.36713/epra2013

EPRA International Journal of

MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH

Monthly, Peer Reviewed (Refereed) & Indexed International Journal

Volume - 9 Issue - 10 October 2023

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ISSN (Online) : 2455 - 3662
SJIF Impact Factor(2023) :8.224
ISI I.F. Value : 1.188
DOI : 10.36713/epra2013

EPRA International Journal of
**Multidisciplinary
Research**

Monthly Peer Reviewed & Indexed
International Online Journal

Volume: 9 Issue: 10 October 2023

Indexed By:

Published By :EPRA Publishing

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MEEKLY π -NORMAL SPACES IN GENERAL TOPOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, A new generalization of normality called meekly π -normality is introduced and studied which is a simultaneous generalization of π -normality and β -normality. Interrelation among some existing variants of normal spaces is discussed and characterizations of meekly π -normal space with some existing variants of normal spaces are obtained.

Mathematics Subject Classification 2020 : 54D10, 54D15

KEYWORDS : β -normal, π -normal, almost normal, meekly normal, softly regular, κ -normal, $\kappa\beta$ -normal.

1. INTRODUCTION

Normality plays a prominent role in general topology. In 1968, Zaitsev [25] introduced the notion of quasi normality is a weaker form of normality and obtained its properties. In 1970, the concept of almost normality was introduced by Singal and Arya [16]. In 1973, the notion of mild normality was introduced by Shchepin [20] and, Singal and Singal [17] independently. In 2011, Arhangel'skii and Ludwig [1] introduced the concept of α -normal and β -normal spaces and obtained their properties. Eva Murtinovain [15] provided an example of a β -normal Tychonoff space which is not normal. In 2002, Kohli and Das [10] introduced θ -normal topological spaces and obtained their characterizations. In 2008, Kalantan [9] introduced π -normal topological spaces and obtained their characterizations. In 2015, Sharma and Kumar [22] introduced a new class of normal spaces called softly normal and obtained a characterization of softly normal space. In 2018, Kumar and Sharma [12] introduced the concepts of softly regular and partly regular spaces and obtained some characterizations of softly regular spaces. In 2023, Kumar [13] introduced the concepts of epi π -normal spaces, which lies between epi-normal and epi-almost normal spaces, and epi-normal and epi-quasi normal spaces. Interrelation among some existing variants of normal spaces is discussed and characterizations of epi π -normal space with some existing variants of normal spaces are obtained.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Let X be a topological space and let $A \subset X$. Throughout the present paper the **closure** of a set A will be denoted by $\text{cl}(A)$ and the **interior** by $\text{int}(A)$. A set $U \subset X$ is said to be **regularly open** [14] if $U = \text{int}(\text{cl}(U))$. The complement of a regularly open set is called **regularly closed**. The finite union of regular open sets is said to be **π -open** [25]. The complement of a π -open set is said to be **π -closed**. A topological space is said to be **normal** [3, 7, 8] if for any pair of disjoint-closed subsets A and B of X can be separated. A space is **k-normal** [20] (**mildly normal** [17]) if for every pair of disjoint regularly closed sets E, F of X there exist disjoint open subsets U and V of X such that $E \subset U$ and $F \subset V$. A topological space is said to be **almost normal** [16] if for every pair of disjoint closed sets A and B one of which is regularly closed, there exist disjoint open sets U and V such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. A topological space is said to be **π -normal** [9] if for every pair of disjoint closed sets A and B , one of which is π -closed, there exist disjoint open sets U and V such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. A topological space X is said to be **almost regular** [16] if for every regularly closed set A and a point $x \notin A$, there exist disjoint open sets U and V such that $A \subset U$ and $x \in V$. A topological space is said to be **softly regular** [12] if for every π -closed set A and a point $x \notin A$, there exist two open sets U and V such that $x \in U$, $A \subset V$, and $U \cap V = \emptyset$. A topological space X is said to be **α -normal** [1] if for any two disjoint closed subsets A and B of X , there exist disjoint open subsets U and V of X such that $A \cap U$ is dense in A and $B \cap U$ is dense in B . A space X is **β -normal** [1] if for any two disjoint closed subsets A and B of X , there exist open subsets U and V of X such that $A \cap U$ is dense in A , $B \cap U$ is dense in B , and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$. A topological space is called **almost β -normal** [5] if for every pair of disjoint closed sets A and B , one of which is regularly closed, there exist disjoint open sets U and V such that $\text{cl}(U \cap A) = A$, $\text{cl}(V \cap B) = B$, and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$. A topological space X is said to

be **βk -normal** [19] if for every pair of disjoint regularly closed subsets A and B of X , there exist disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $\text{cl}(A \cap U) = A$, $\text{cl}(B \cap U) = B$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$. A space X is said to be **semi-normal** if for every closed set A contained in an open set U , there exists a regularly open set V such that $A \subset V \subset U$.

3. MEEKLY π -NORMAL

Definition 3.1. A topological space is called **meekly π -normal** if for every pair of disjoint closed sets A and B , one of which is π -closed, there exist disjoint open sets U and V such that $\text{cl}(U \cap A) = A$, $\text{cl}(V \cap B) = B$, and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$.

From the definitions it is obvious that every normal space is π -normal and every π -normal space is meekly π -normal.

Theorem 3.2. Every π -normal space is meekly π -normal.

Proof. Let X be a π -normal space. Let A and B be two disjoint closed sets in X , one of which (say A) is π -closed. Since X is π -normal there exist disjoint open sets W and V containing A and B respectively. Since $W \cap V = \emptyset$, $W \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$. Let $U = \text{int}(A)$. Then $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$, $\text{cl}(U \cap A) = A$, and $\text{cl}(V \cap B) = B$. So, the space is meekly π -normal.

The following implications hold but none are reversible.

normal \Rightarrow π -normal \Rightarrow almost normal \Rightarrow k -normal

\Downarrow \Downarrow \Downarrow \Downarrow

β -normal \Rightarrow meekly π -normal \Rightarrow almost β -normal \Rightarrow βk -normal

Example 3.3. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{c, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$. Then the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is not meekly π -normal since for π -closed $A = \{a, b\}$ and disjoint closed set $B = \{d\}$, there does not exist two open sets U and V such that $\text{cl}(U \cap A) = A$, $\text{cl}(B \cap V) = B$, and $U \cap V = \emptyset$.

Example 3.4. Let X be the union of any infinite set Y and two distinct one point sets p and q . The modified Fort space on X as defined in [23] is almost β -normal as well as $k\beta$ -normal but not β -normal. In X any subset of Y is open and any set containing p or q open if and only if it contains all but a finite number of points in Y . This space is not β -normal even not α -normal [1] because for disjoint closed sets $\{p\}$ and $\{q\}$ there does not exist two disjoint open sets separating them. The regularly closed sets of this space are finite subsets of Y and sets of the form $A \cup \{p, q\}$, where $A \subset Y$ is infinite. Thus the space is almost β -normal.

Arhangel'skii and Ludwig [1] have shown that a space is normal if and only if it is κ -normal and β -normal. Therefore, every non-normal space which is almost normal is an example of a κ -normal, almost β -normal space which is not β -normal.

Recall that a Hausdorff space X is said to be **extremally disconnected** if the closure of every open set in X is open.

A point $x \in X$ is called a **θ -limit point** [24] of A if every closed neighbourhood of x intersects A . Let $\text{cl}_\theta(A)$ denotes the set of all θ -limit points of A . The set A is called θ -closed if $A = \text{cl}_\theta(A)$.

Definition 3.5. A topological space X is said to be

- (i) **θ -normal** [10] if every pair of disjoint closed sets one of which is θ -closed are contained in disjoint open sets;
- (ii) **Weakly θ -normal ($w\theta$ -normal)** [10] if every pair of disjoint θ -closed sets are contained in disjoint open sets.

Theorem 3.6. Every extremally disconnected meekly π -normal space is π -normal.

Proof. Let X be an extremally disconnected meekly π -normal space and let A be a π -closed set disjoint from the closed set B . By meekly π -normality of X , there exist disjoint open sets U and V such that $\text{cl}(U \cap A) = A$, $\text{cl}(V \cap B) = B$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$. Thus $A \subset \text{cl}(U)$ and $B \subset \text{cl}(V)$. By the extremally disconnectedness of X , $\text{cl}(U)$ and $\text{cl}(V)$ are disjoint open sets containing A and B respectively.

Theorem 3.7. Every T_1 almost β -normal space is almost regular [5].

Theorem 3.8. Every T_1 meekly π -normal space is softly regular.

Proof. Let A be a π -closed set in X and x be a point outside A . Since X is a T_1 -space and every singleton is closed in a T_1 -space, by meekly π -normality there exist disjoint open sets U and V such that $x \in U$, $\text{cl}(V \cap A) = A$, $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$. Since $A \subset \text{cl}(V)$, U and $X - \text{cl}(U)$ are disjoint open sets containing $\{x\}$ and A , respectively. Thus, the space is softly regular.

Corollary 3.9. Every T_1 meekly π -normal space is almost regular.

Proof. Since every softly regular space is almost regular, so proof is easy.

Theorem 3.10. An almost regular weakly θ -normal space is mildly normal space [11].

Corollary 3.11. A softly regular weakly θ -normal space is mildly normal space

Proof. Since every softly regular space is almost regular, so proof is easy.

Corollary 3.12. In a T_1 -space, weak θ -normality and meekly π -normality implies mildly normality.

Proof. Let X be a T_1 weakly θ -normal, meekly π -normal space. Then by Corollary 3.9, X is almost regular. Since every softly regular weakly θ -normal space is κ -normal, so X is κ -normal.

Corollary 3.13. In the class of T_1 , θ -normal spaces, every meekly π -normal space is π -normal.

Proof. Let X be a T_1 space which is θ -normal as well as meekly π -normal. Since every T_1 meekly π -normal space is softly regular, so X is π -normal.

Corollary 3.14. In the class of T_1 , paracompact spaces, every meekly π -normal space is π -normal.

Proof. Since every paracompact space is θ -normal [10], the result holds by Corollary 3.13.

Recall that a space X is said to be **almost compact** [4] if every open cover of X has a finite subcollection, the closure of whose members covers X .

Corollary 3.15. An almost compact, meekly π -normal, T_1 -space is κ -normal.

Proof. The proof is immediate from the result Theorem 3.8 of Singal and Singal [17] and since every T_1 meekly π -normal space is almost regular that an almost regular almost compact space is κ -normal.

Corollary 3.16. A Lindelöf, meekly π -normal, T_1 -space is κ -normal.

Proof. Since an almost regular Lindelöf space is κ -normal [17], and since every T_1 meekly π -normal space is almost regular, the proof is immediate

Remark 3.17. The T_1 axiom in the above theorem cannot be relaxed since there exist meekly π -normal spaces which are not almost regular.

Example 3.18. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \emptyset, X\}$. Then X is vacuously normal, thus meekly π -normal but not almost regular as the regularly closed set $\{a, b\}$ and any point outside it cannot be separated by disjoint open sets.

Theorem 3.19. In the class of T_1 , semi-normal spaces, every meekly π -normal space is regular.

Proof. Let X be a T_1 , semi-normal, and meekly π -normal space. Let A be a closed subset of X and $x \notin A$. Since X is a T_1 -space, the singleton set $\{x\}$ is closed. So by semi-normality of X , there exists a regularly open set U such that $\{x\} \subset U \subset X - A$. Here $F = X - U$ is a regularly closed set containing A with $x \notin F$. As X is a meekly π -normal T_1 -space, X is softly regular by Theorem 3.7. Thus there exist disjoint open sets V and W such that $x \in V$ and $A \subset F \subset W$. Hence X is regular.

The following theorem provides a characterization of meekly π -normality.

Theorem 3.20. For any topological space X , the following are equivalent:

(1). X is meekly π -normal;

(2). whenever $E, F \subset X$ are disjoint closed sets and E is π -closed, there is an open set V such that $F = \text{cl}(V \cap F)$ and $E \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$;

(3). whenever $E \subset X$ is closed, $U \subset X$ is π -open, and $E \subset U$, there is an open set V such that $E = \text{cl}(E \cap V) \subset \text{cl}(V) \subset U$.

Proof. [(1) \Rightarrow (2)]. Suppose that $E, F \subset X$ are disjoint closed sets and E is π -closed. Since X is meekly π -normal, there exist open sets U and V such that $E = \text{cl}(U \cap E) \subset \text{cl}(U)$, $F = \text{cl}(V \cap F) \subset \text{cl}(V)$, and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$. Then $E \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$.

[(2) \Rightarrow (1)]. Suppose that $E, F \subset X$ are disjoint closed sets and E is π -closed. By the assumption, there exists an open set V such that $F = \text{cl}(V \cap F)$ and $E \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$. Let $U = \text{int}(E)$. Then $E = \text{cl}(U \cap E)$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = E \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$.

[(1) \Rightarrow (3)]. Suppose that E is closed, U is π -open, and $E \subset U$. Since U is π -open, $X - U$ is π -closed. Since X is meekly π -normal, there are open sets O and V such that $X - U = \text{cl}(O \cap (X - U)) \subset O$, $E = \text{cl}(V \cap E) \subset \text{cl}(V)$, and $\text{cl}(O) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$. Then $(X - U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$ which means that $\text{cl}(V) \subset U$.

[(3) \Rightarrow (2)]. Suppose that $E, F \subset X$ are disjoint closed sets and E is π -closed. Then $F \subset X - E$ and $X - E$ is π -open. By the hypothesis, there is an open set V such that $F = \text{cl}(V \cap F) \subset \text{cl}(V) \subset X - E$. Then $\text{cl}(V) \cap E = \emptyset$, as desired.

The following result gives a decomposition of meekly π -normality.

Theorem 3.21. A space is π -normal if and only if it is meekly π -normal and quasi normal.

Proof. Let X be a meekly π -normal and quasi normal space. Let A and B be two disjoint closed sets in X in which A is π -closed. By meekly π -normality of X , there exist disjoint open sets U and V such that $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$, $\text{cl}(A \cap U) = A$ and $\text{cl}(B \cap V) = B$. Thus $A \subset \text{cl}(U)$ and $B \subset \text{cl}(V)$. Here $\text{cl}(U)$ and $\text{cl}(V)$ are disjoint π -closed sets. So by quasi normality, there exist disjoint open sets W_1 and W_2 such that $\text{cl}(U) \subset W_1$ and $\text{cl}(V) \subset W_2$. Hence X is π -normal.

Corollary 3.22. In a semi-normal and quasi normal space the following statements are equivalent :

- (1). X is normal;
- (2). X is π -normal;
- (3). X is β -normal;
- (4). X is meekly π -normal.

Proof. (1) \Rightarrow (3) \Rightarrow (4) and (1) \Rightarrow (2) \Rightarrow (4) are obvious.

[(4) \Rightarrow (1)]. Let X be semi-normal, quasi normal and meekly π -normal space. We have to show X is normal. By Theorem 3.21, X is π -normal. Since every π -normal, semi-normal space is normal, so X is normal.

Theorem 3.23. Every semi-normal, meekly π -normal space is α -normal.

Proof. Let X be a semi-normal, meekly π -normal space. Let A and B be two disjoint closed sets in X . Thus $A \subset (X - B)$. By semi-normality, there exists a π -open set F such that $A \subset F \subset (X - B)$. Now A and $(X - F)$ are two disjoint closed sets in X in which $X - F$ is a π -closed set containing B . Thus by meekly π -normality, there exist disjoint open sets U and V such that $\text{cl}(U \cap A) = A$, $\text{cl}((X - F) \cap V) = X - F$, and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$. Here $A = \text{cl}(U \cap A) \subset \text{cl}(U)$ and $(X - F) = \text{cl}((X - F) \cap V) \subset \text{cl}(V)$. Thus U and $W = X - \text{cl}(U)$ are two disjoint open sets such that $\text{cl}(U \cap A) = A$ and $B \subset W$. Therefore, $\text{cl}(W \cap B) = B$ and X is α -normal.

Theorem 3.24. Suppose that X and Y are topological spaces, X is meekly π -normal, and $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is onto, continuous, open, and closed. Then Y is meekly π -normal.

Proof. Suppose that $E, F \subset Y$ are disjoint closed sets and E is π -closed. Since f is continuous, $f^{-1}(E)$ and $f^{-1}(F)$ are disjoint closed sets. To see that $f^{-1}(E) = \text{cl}(f^{-1}(\text{int}(E)))$, suppose that $W \subset X$ is open such that $W \cap f^{-1}(E) \neq \emptyset$. Then $f(W)$ is open in Y and $f(W) \cap E = f(W) \cap \text{cl}(\text{int}(E)) \neq \emptyset$ which implies that $f(W) \cap \text{int}(E) \neq \emptyset$. Hence, $W \cap f^{-1}(\text{int}(E)) \neq \emptyset$ and so $f^{-1}(E) = \text{cl}(f^{-1}(\text{int}(E)))$. Since $f^{-1}(E) = \text{cl}(f^{-1}(\text{int}(E)))$, $f^{-1}(E)$ is a π -closed set. So there exists an open set $U \subset X$ such that $f^{-1}(F) = \text{cl}(f^{-1}(F) \cap U)$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap f^{-1}(E) = \emptyset$. Since $\text{cl}(U) \cap f^{-1}(E) = \emptyset$, $f(\text{cl}(U)) \cap E = \emptyset$. Also, note that $f(U)$ is open and $f(\text{cl}(U))$ is closed. Since $f(\text{cl}(U))$ is a closed set containing $f(U)$, $\text{cl}(f(U)) \subset f(\text{cl}(U))$. So $\text{cl}(f(U)) \cap E = \emptyset$. It remains to show that $F = \text{cl}(F \cap f(U))$. To see this, let $y \in F$ and O be an open set containing y . Then $f^{-1}(y) \in [f^{-1}(F) \cap f^{-1}(O)]$. Since $f^{-1}(F) = \text{cl}(f^{-1}(F) \cap U)$, $f^{-1}(F) \cap U \cap f^{-1}(O) \neq \emptyset$. Hence, $F \cap f(U) \cap O = f(f^{-1}(F) \cap f(U) \cap f^{-1}(O)) \supset f[f^{-1}(F) \cap U \cap f^{-1}(O)] \neq \emptyset$, as desired.

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